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OBSERVATIONAL STUDIES

An Observational Report about the Detoxifying Effects of Calcium Hypochlorite (MMS2) on Graphene Oxides (GOs) in Human Plasma

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ABSTRACT

Graphene Oxide (GO) is known to have two faces: it has many benefits; and it is hazardous to our health. This study understood the jeopardizing effects of GOs in our body, and wanted to find out a way to remove GOs in our body. Three sets of observational studies were done to evaluate the detoxifying effects of MMS2 (Calcium Hypochlorite), Hydroxychloroquine (HCQ), ivermectin, and GNP (Gold Nanoparticle) + Camostat Mesylate (Foipan) on Graphene Oxide (GO) in the human plasma. MMS2 solution showed almost clear removal of GOs in the human plasma while GNP + Foipan made questionable removal effects of GOs in the human blood. This article presents MMS2 solution as an inexpensive agent to remove magnetic graphene nanoparticles in the human blood. Currently, MMS2 is included in detoxifying treatments for the sequelae of COVID-19 experimental injections and for people who have many GOs in their blood and experience shedding symptoms.

Introduction

Graphene Oxide (GO) is known to have benefits for biomedical applications because it can be used for drug delivery, [1] biosensing, [2] and killing of COVID-19 viruses [3]. GO is well-known main component of COVID-19 vaccines [4-7]. GO is also known as cytotoxic, inhibits cell proliferation, and causes many lethal impacts on human tissues [8]. La Quinta Columna argued that glutathione successfully removed magnetic graphene nanoparticles in an inexpensive way [9]. Glutathione (GSH) acts as a vital regulator in the regulation of cellular oxidative stresses and affects intracellular reductive/oxidative balance and cellular viability and proliferation [10], and is included in the lists of detoxifying agents for GOs in the bloods and for alleviating sequelae of COVID-19 experimental injections [11].

Three series of observational researches were done to evaluate if MMS2 (Master Mineral Solution 2, Calcium hypochlorite) can be another inexpensive candidate for the detoxification of GOs in the plasma and for relieving symptoms of the COVID-19 vaccine sequelae.

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Materials and Methods

Three series of observational studies were done for this purpose. First, in a vivo study, two people took MMS2 at least for a month and compared the number of graphene oxides in their bloods before and after the treatment. In a vitro study, these two people's bloods were treated with MMS2 on the petri dish for a month and the number of graphene oxide were counted two times, before and after the MMS2 treatment. Second, six groups of 42 blood samples, twelve blood samples from people of COVID-19 experimental jab un-injected and 30 blood samples from injected, were prepared and each group was treated for 4 weeks with different sets of medications, all of which were already known as a detoxifying agent for COVID-19 experimental injections. Third, two blood samples from each person and fourteen blood samples from seven people were prepared. They were treated for two weeks either with MMS2 or with GNP + Foipan and were observed two times before and after the treatment.

The materials of the treatment solution were purchased as was written in the previous article [11]. Bottled water of 500 cc which has the brand name of Jeju SamDaSoo was purchased. It contained minerals of calcium 2.5-4.0 mg/L, kalium 1.5-3.4 mg/L, natrium 4.0-7.2 mg/L, magnesium 1.7-3.5 mg/L, and no fluoride. GNP of 250 cc bottle has the brand name of "Medigold" (michael@nutraneering.com) and was purchased from the United States of America. Calcium hypochlorite, HCQ (hydroxychloroquine 200 mg/tablet), Ivermectin (12 mg/tablet), and Foipan (100 mg Camostat Mesylates/tablet) were purchased in the Republic of Korea. MMS2 of 5% storage solution was made by mixing 12 grams of Calcium Hypochlorite into the 500 cc of bottled water. MMS2 treatment solution was made by mixing 20 drops of 5% MMS2 storage solution into the 500 cc of bottled water.

First observational study

This study was done to preview the effect of MMS2 on the GO (graphene oxide) in the bloods of people because MMS1 was said to be effective in the detoxification or relieving the side symptoms or sequelae of COVID-19 experimental injections. Two people took MMS2 for 4 weeks and compared the number of graphene oxides in the bloods before and after. One person was COVID-19 experimental jab injected twice and PCR were done three times and the other person did neither injected nor PCR. Their bloods were sampled before they took MMS2, centrifuged

for 30 minutes at 2,500 RPM, upper portions were collected, treated with MMS2 thrice a week for a month, and observed their graphene numbers before and after one month of MMS2 treatments. For in vivo study, their bloods were recollected after one month of MMS2 treatment.

Second observational study

This observational study was done to identify any effective agent among known detoxifying agents for the sequelae of COVID-19 experimental injections and to comparatively evaluate their abilities of detoxifying or eliminating GO from the bloods of people whether they took COVID-19 experimental injections or not. All 42 blood samples including twelve of COVID-19 experimental jab un-injected people and 30 of injected people were randomly divided into six groups and each group had two injected and five non-injected blood samples. Each group was treated for 4 weeks according to the treatment schedule. The treatment of each group was done as follows: the first group of blood samples in the petri dishes was treated thrice a week with a submerging solution of MMS2 treating solution consists of 500 cc bottled water + 20 drops of 5% MMS2; the second group of MMS2 + Foipan was treated thrice a week with a submerging solution of 500 cc bottled water + 20 drops of 5% MMS2 + 5 tablets of Foipan; the third group of HCQ treatment was treated thrice a week with a submerging solution of 500 cc bottled water + 5 tablets of HCQ; the fourth group of Ivermectin treatment was treated thrice a week with a submerging solution of 500 cc bottled water + 5 tablets of Ivermectin; the fifth group of HCQ + Ivermectin treatment was treated thrice a week with a submerging solution of 500 cc bottled water + 5 tablets of HCQ + 5 tablets of Ivermectin + 5 tablets of Foipan; and the sixth group was treated thrice a week with a submerging solution of 250 cc bottled water + 250 cc of purchased GNP solution + 5 tablets of Foipan.

Third observational study

This study was done to evaluate the comparative power of detoxifying effects between the MMS2 and GNP + Foipan and to see whether the detoxifying effects of the MMS2 or GNP + Foipan could be changed among people with the different immunity and characteristics. Twelve blood samples of 6 people (two COVID-19 experimental non-injected and four injected) were randomly divided into two groups as the same blood of each person should be in the different group; one group was treated thrice a week for two weeks with a submerging solution of 500 cc

bottled water + 20 drops of 5% MMS2; and the other group was treated thrice a week for two weeks with a submerging solution of 250 cc bottled water + 250 cc of purchased GNP solution + 5 tablets of Foipan.

Results

First observational study

The first case of the first observational study was a 55-year-old, 48 Kg, female, who had a COVID-19 experimental injection only one time with Pfizer experimental vaccine and three PCR tests. Before the experimental injection, she was healthy, and had regular health checks all of which showed normal, looked younger than her age. She had her 1st Pfizer Vaccination, on 10:40 AM, August 10, 2021, and then in the next morning, she felt her chest tightness, dyspnea, palpitations, dizziness, dyspnea, and she visited ER, but no disease entity was identified. She was officially enlisted as a person who had severe sequelae of the COVID experimental injection. She then visited several ERs including several university ERs, but there were only temporary alleviations. Her symptoms only aggravated and she stopped her

civil service position for 6 months to be treated. She visited several famous places including Ha-dong clinic to detoxify herself from the sequelae from the COVID-19 experimental injection. She visited my clinic and admitted from February 24, 2022, and she was treated by the COVID-vaccine (experimental injection) detoxification method and her symptoms slowly improved [6]. She began to take MMS2 from one drop a day and slowly increased to 6 drops a day from June 6, 2022. She reported that her brain fog and chest tightness were a little relieved (from 6 to 3, where 10 is the severest) after MMS2 ingestion for two weeks. She had blood examination on that day and her plasma findings showed many GOs: GO length of less than 30 micrometers: 251 pieces, GO length between 30 ~ 70 micrometers: 140 pieces; GO length of larger than 70 micrometers: 52 pieces; and gold-colored GO: 112 pieces. The pictures of her typical GOs before the MMS2 treatment are shown here (Figures 1a-1d).

After a month of her 6 drop-a-day MMS2 ingestion, he checked his blood on July 9, 2022. There were no demonstrable abnormalities of her blood chemistry except for the change of the BUN

Figure 1 a: A partially melted 1,222-micrometer-length GO with branches. 1b: A partially melted 744-micrometer-length GO with one knot. 1c: A thin 450-micrometer-length GO. 1d: Multiple 114-, 67-, 54-micrometer-sized GO particles with over 30 dotted particles.

from 16 (normal < 20) to 21 (abnormal > 20) as shown in the table even after she took MMS2 for a month (Table 1).

There was a 73-85% reductions of the number of GOs in the petri dish of her plasma: number of GOs of less than 30 micrometer-length: 225 (decreased by 10%); GOs of 30-70 micrometer-length: 40 (decreased by 71%); GOs of longer than 70 micrometer-length: 24 (decreased by 54%); and gold-colored GOs: 11 (decreased by 90%) (Figures 2a-2d).

The second case of the first observational study was a 66-year-old, 63 Kg, male, who had no COVID-19 experimental injections and no PCR test was done. He was healthy, and had hypertension and hyperlipidemia, but looked younger than his age. He had no demonstrable abnormal symptoms. He began to take MMS2 from one drop a day and slowly increased to 8 drops a day from June 5, 2022. He had blood examination one day before of MMS2 treatment and the petri dish of his plasma findings showed many GOs: GO length of less than 30 micrometers: 295 pieces, GO length between 30 ~ 70 micrometers: 368 pieces; GO length of larger than 70 micrometers: 203 pieces; and gold-colored GO: 221 pieces. The pictures of his typical GOs before the MMS2 treatment

are shown here (Figures 3a-3d).

After a month of his 8 drop-a-day MMS2 ingestion, he checked his blood on July 9, 2022.

There were no demonstrable abnormalities of his blood chemistry and peripheral blood tests as shown in the table 2 even after he took MMS2 for a month 8 drops a day except for the changes of percentage of monocyte from 11.9% (abnormal as > 10) to 9.4% (normal), gamma-GTP from 75 (abnormal > 70) to 72 (abnormal > 70), glucose from 92 (normal) to 113 (abnormal > 99), and BUN from 18 (normal) to 21 (abnormal > 20). There was a 73-85% reductions of the number of GOs in the petri dish of his plasma: number of GOs of less than 30 micrometer-length: 301 (increase by 102%); GOs of 30-70 micrometer-length: 55 (decreased by 85%); GOs of longer than 70 micrometer-length: 36 (decreased by 83%); and gold-colored GOs: 60 (decreased by 63%) (Figures 4a-4d).

Second observational study

First group of MMS2 treatment: All seven plasma samples from two COVID-19 experimental solution un-injected and five injected people showed similar patterns after MMS2 treatments.

Blood Chemistry, U/A, TFT:			July 8th.	June 4th.	May 13th.	April 25th	
Female, 55-y-o	치명병	참고치	단위	2022-07-08	2022-06-04	2022-05-13	2022-04-25
	D-dimer-[일반면역검사](정상) / 웹(ED...	≤ 0.50	mg/L FEU	0.30	0.32	0.44	0.31
	비타민-[정밀면역검사]_D3 / Serum	Deficiency <...	ng/mL	50.2			57.5
	일반혈액검사(CBC)-[혈구세포-중비 측정]	3.9 - 9.8	*10 ³ /μl	5.5	4.4	4.8	3.6(▼)
	일반혈액검사(CBC)-[혈구세포-중비 측정]	3.9 - 9.8	*10 ⁶ /μl	4.18	4.17	3.96	4.13
	일반혈액검사(CBC)-[혈구세포-중비 측정]	12 - 16	g/dl	12.3	12.5	11.9(▼)	12.2
	일반혈액검사(CBC)-[혈구세포-중비 측정]	36 - 49	X	37.4	37.2	34.8(▼)	35.9(▼)
	일반혈액검사(CBC)-[혈구세포-중비 측정]	150 - 450	*10 ³ /μl	356	227	237	302
	백혈구백분율(혈액)-[혈구세포-중비 측정]			Seg. Neutroph...	Seg. Neutroph...	Seg. Neutroph...	Seg. Neutroph...
	Segment neutrophil	40 - 75	X	43.9	30.5(▼)	26.1(▼)	31.2(▼)
	Lymphocyte	20 - 45	X	44.4	53.4(▲)	56.2(▲)	51.0(▲)
	Monocyte	0 - 10	X	8.7	8.8	6.5	8.4
	Eosinophil	0 - 6	X	2.5	6.6(▲)	10.2(▲)	8.6(▲)
	Basophil	0 - 2	X	0.5	0.7	1.0	0.8
	알부민[화학반응-중비 측정][정량] / Se...	70 - 99	mg/dL	92	100(▲)	86	92
	총단백질량[화학반응-중비 측정] / Serum	6.5 - 8.5	g/dL	6.7	6.9	6.7	7.1
	알부민[화학반응-중비 측정] / Serum	3.2 - 5.5	g/dL	4.4	4.1	4.0	4.4
	간해당[화학반응-중비 측정]_총합 / S...	8.6 - 10.2	mg/dL	9.3	9.0	9.4	9.3
	간해당[화학반응-중비 측정]_인 / Serum	2.5 - 5	mg/dL	4.7	4.4	4.7	5.1(▲)
	총빌리루빈정량[화학반응-중비 측정] / ...	<1.40	mg/dL	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.2
	AST (SGOT) [화학반응-중비 측정] / Serum	≤ 40	IU/L	18	66(▲)	20	104(▲)
	ALT (SGPT) [화학반응-중비 측정] / Serum	≤ 41	IU/L	13	19	12	30
	알부민포스파타제 [화학반응-중비 측정] ...	35 - 129	IU/L	17(▼)	11(▼)	16(▼)	<10(▼)
	γ-GTP [화학반응-중비 측정] / Serum	6 - 42	IU/L	14	9	7	<3(▼)
	콜레스테롤-총콜레스테롤정량[화학반응] ...	Desirable <...	mg/dL	168	161	135	154
	지질[화학반응-중비 측정]-트리글리세리...	Normal: < 150	mg/dL	74	137	77	109
	콜레스테롤-HDL 콜레스테롤[화학반응-중...	Low HDL-Chol...	mg/dL	58	53	51	51
	콜레스테롤-LDL 콜레스테롤[화학반응-중...		mg/dL	95	81	69	81
	요소질소[NPN포함][화학반응-중비 측정] ...	6 - 20	mg/dL	21(▲)	16	15	10
	크레아티닌[화학반응-중비 측정] / Serum	0.5 - 1.2	mg/dL	1.00	0.8	0.6	0.7
	요소산[화학반응-중비 측정] / Serum	2.6 - 6	mg/dL	3.9	2.9	2.6	2.1(▼)
	감상선호르몬 분[정밀면역검사]_트리요...	80 - 200	ng/dL	97	103	109	123
	감상선호르몬 분[정밀면역검사]_유리싸...	0.93 - 1.7	ng/dL	1.28	1.54	1.35	1.33
	감상선자극호르몬[정밀면역검사]_감상...	0.27 - 4.2	uIU/mL	0.90	1.71	4.84(▲)	2.89
	RA factor-[일반면역검사]-(정상) / Se...						
CRP-정상-C 반응성단백-[일반](정상) / ...	Negative						

* There were no demonstrable changes in the laboratory test results between before and after the MMS2 treatments.

Table 1 Blood chemistry recordings of the first case of a 55-year-old female She checked her blood before the treatment on June 4th and one month after the treatment on July 8, 2022. There were no demonstrable abnormalities of her blood chemistry except for the change of the BUN from 16 (normal < 20) to 21 (abnormal > 20) even after she took MMS2 for a month.

Figure 2 a A w-shaped 1,497-micrometer-length GO. 2b: Linear 16-, 23-micrometer-sized GOs with over 30 dotted particles. 2c: Dotted islands of 61-, 73-micrometer-length GOs and small particles. 2d: Linear 557-micrometer-sized GO.

Male, 66-year-old		Blood Chemistry, U/A, Thyroid Function; July 9th ; June 4th			
치명명	참고치	단위	2022-07-09	2022-06-04	
D-dimer 0.33, 0.35	D-dimer-[일반면역검사](정상) / WB(ED...)	≤ 0.50	mg/L FEU	0.33	0.35
	일반혈액검사(CBC)-[혈구세포-장비 측정 ...]	3.9 ~ 9.8	+10 ⁻³ /μL	5.3	4.9
	일반혈액검사(CBC)-[혈구세포-장비 측정 ...]	4.2 ~ 6.5	+10 ⁻⁶ /μL	5.31	4.94
	일반혈액검사(CBC)-[혈구세포-장비 측정 ...]	13 ~ 18	g/dL	15.2	14.2
	일반혈액검사(CBC)-[혈구세포-장비 측정 ...]	38 ~ 54	%	46.2	44.3
	일반혈액검사(CBC)-[혈구세포-장비 측정 ...]	150 ~ 450	+10 ⁻³ /μL	205	184
	백혈구백분율(혈액)-[혈구세포-장비측...			Seg. Neutroph...	Seg. Neutroph...
	Segment neutrophil	40 ~ 75	%	52.0	52.0
	Lymphocyte	20 ~ 45	%	35.7	33.9
monocyte, 9.4%, 11.9%	Monocyte	0 ~ 10	%	9.4	11.9(▲)
	Eosinophil	0 ~ 6	%	2.3	1.8
	Basophil	0 ~ 2	%	0.6	0.4
blood sugar, 113, 93	당검사[화학반응-장비 측정][정량] / Se...	70 ~ 99	mg/dL	113(▲)	93
	총단백질량[화학반응-장비 측정] / Serum	6.5 ~ 8.5	g/dL	7.8	6.8
	알부민[화학반응-장비 측정] / Serum	3.2 ~ 5.5	g/dL	4.6	4.0
	견해질[화학반응-장비 측정]_총합합 / S...	8.6 ~ 10.2	mg/dL	9.9	9.0
	견해질[화학반응-장비 측정]_인 / Serum	2.5 ~ 5	mg/dL	4.0	4.9
	총빌리루빈정량[화학반응-장비 측정] / ...	<1.40	mg/dL	0.3	0.3
	AST (SGOT) [화학반응-장비 측정] / Serum	≤ 40	IU/L	33	26
	ALT (SGPT) [화학반응-장비 측정] / Serum	≤ 41	IU/L	38	32
	알칼리포스파타제 [화학반응-장비 측정] ...	35 ~ 129	IU/L	88	73
γ-glutamyl transpeptidase) July (72), June (75)	γ-GTP [화학반응-장비 측정] / Serum	10 ~ 71	IU/L	72(▲)	75(▲)
	클레스테롤-총클레스테롤정량[화학반응...	Desirable <...	mg/dL	224	190
	지질 [화학반응-장비 측정]-트리글리세라...	Normal: < 150	mg/dL	192	150
	클레스테롤-HDL클레스테롤 [화학반응-장...	Low HDL-Chol...	mg/dL	57	49
	클레스테롤-LDL클레스테롤 [화학반응-장...		mg/dL	129	111
	요소질소 [NPN포함] [화학반응-장비 측정] ...	6 ~ 20	mg/dL	21(▲)	18
	크레아티닌 [화학반응-장비 측정] / Serum	0.5 ~ 1.2	mg/dL	1.02	0.9
	요산 [화학반응-장비 측정] / Serum	3.5 ~ 7.2	mg/dL	5.9	6.1
	요 일반검사[화학반응-장비 측정]-10중...			S.G : 1.018...	S.G : 1.021...
	갑상선호르몬 등 [정밀면역검사]-트리요...	80 ~ 200	ng/dL	139	93
	갑상선호르몬 등 [정밀면역검사]-유리싸...	0.93 ~ 1.7	ng/dL	1.20	1.14
	갑상선자극호르몬 [정밀면역검사]-갑상...	0.27 ~ 4.2	uIU/mL	1.19	2.53
	알파파티프 로틴-[정밀면역검사]-알파파...	0.6 ~ 7	ng/mL	3.72	
Vitamin D, 55.7	비타민-D [정밀면역검사]_03 / Serum	Deficiency <...	ng/mL		55.7
	헤모글로빈A1C-[정밀분광-질량분석] / ...	0 ~ 0			Hb A1c : 5.5...
	HbA1c-NGSP	정상: ≤5.6	%		5.5
	HbA1c-eAG	참고치 미설정	mg/dL		111

*** There were no demonstrable changes in the laboratory test results between before and after the MMS2 treatments.**

Table 2 Blood chemistry recordings of the second case of a 66-year-old male He checked his blood before the treatment on June 4th and one month after the treatment on July 9, 2022. There were no demonstrable abnormalities of his blood chemistry and peripheral blood tests except for the changes of percentage of monocyte from 11.9% (abnormal as > 10) to 9.4% (normal as < 10), gamma-GTP from 75 (abnormal > 70) to 72 (abnormal > 70), glucose from 92 (normal) to 113 (abnormal > 99), and BUN from 18 (normal) to 21 (abnormal > 20).

Figure 3 a: A partially melted very long (> 2 mm) GO. 3b: A shield-like GO of 519- micrometer in width and 417-micrometer in length shown in the blood of a person who was not COVID-19 experimental injection injected and did not have a PCR test before the MMS2 treatment. 3c: A 341-micrometer long, multiples ribs of a pan-shaped GO. 3d: A 1,124-micrometer long GO shown in the blood of a person who was not COVID-19 experimental injection injected and did not have a PCR test before the MMS2 treatment.

Figure 4 a: Various sized GOs including 13-micrometer and 17-micrometer GOs. 4b: A 169-micrometer long GO was found in the blood after one month MMS2 treatment. 4c: Various sized GOs including 69-micrometer and 102-micrometer GOs. 4d: Probable GO remnants of various size and shape were found in the blood after one month MMS2 treatment.

First case of the first group of MMS2 treatment showed almost cleared GOs and only some marginal shape of GOs was remained (all were x 250) (Figures 5a-5c).

Second case of the first group of MMS2 treatment showed almost cleared GOs and only some portions of the ribbon-shaped GOs were remained. The upper left picture is x 100 and the upper right one is x 250 view of the upper left picture. The lower left picture is another area of the MMS2 treated plasma, which showed only trails of disappeared GOs (Figures 6a-6c).

Third case of the first group of MMS2 treatment showed sand-island-like remnant of GOs (x 250) (Figures 7a,b).

Fourth case of the first group of MMS2 treatment showed almost cleared GOs and only some remnants of GOs (x 250) (Figures 8a,b).

Fifth case of the first group of MMS2 treatment showed almost cleared GOs and only some intestine-like remnants of GOs. (Left: x 100, Right: x 250) (Figures 9a,b).

Sixth case of the first group of MMS2 treatment showed small round secondary GOs and lynchpin-like

remnants of un-melted GOs (x 250) (Figures 10a,b).

Second group of MMS2 + Foipan treatment:
All seven plasma samples from two COVID-19 experimental solution un-injected and five injected people showed similar patterns after MMS2 + Foipan treatments.

First case of the second group of MMS2 + Foipan treatment showed scattered islands-like partially un-melted GOs. (Left: x 100, Right: x 250) (Figures 11a,b).

Second case of the second group of MMS2 + Foipan treatment showed scattered islands-like and long-rod-like traces of melted GOs. Black clouds in the picture seem to be Foipan particles. (Left: x 100; Right: x 250) (Figures 12a,b).

Third case of the second group of MMS2 + Foipan treatment showed scattered islands-like and mountain range-like partially melted GOs. Black clouds in the picture seem to be Foipan particles (Left: x 100; Right: x 250) (Figures 13a,b).

Fourth case of the second group of MMS2 + Foipan treatment showed whirlwind-shaped trails of cleared GOs (x 250) (Figures 14a,b).

Figure 5 a: Only traces of probable 860-micrometer GOs are seen. 5b: Probable traces of GOs and some outline remnants on the outside of a 635 x 637 micrometers GO are seen. 5c: Only traces of probable 401-micrometer GOs are seen.

Figure 6 a: Almost cleared GOs and only some portions of the ribbon-shaped GOs were remained (x 100). 6b: Almost cleared portion of GO and only some portions of the ribbon-shaped GOs of 1,170 micrometers which was remained unmelt. This is a x 250 view of the middle portion of the upper left picture. 6c: Another area of the MMS2 treated plasma showed only trails of disappeared GOs of 870 micrometer (x 250).

Figure 7 a: A sand-island-like remnant of melt GOs of 732 x 192 micrometers (x 250). 7b: A round sand-island-like remnant of GOs of 731 micrometers (x 250).

Figure 8 a: Almost cleared GOs with only traces of 174, 125, 100, and 87 micrometer sizes (x 250). 8b: A large island-like remnant of GOs of 1,065 micrometers (x 250).

Figure 9 a: Almost cleared GOs with a group size of 1,183 (x 250). 9a: A large island-like remnant of GOs of 1,065 micrometers (x 250).

Figure 10 a: Three small round secondary GOs and multiple, linchpin-like remnants of un-melted GOs (x 250). 10b: Multiple, linchpin-like remnants of un-melted GOs of 113 and 97 micrometer sizes (x 250).

Figure 11 a: Scattered islands-like traces of melted GOs of various sizes 130, 63, 45, 41 micrometers (x 100). 11b: Large island-like partially melted GOs (x 250).

Figure 12 a: Scattered islands-like spots of unknown materials/or GOs and long-rod-like traces of melted GOs (x 100). 12b: Scattered islands-like spots of unknown materials/or GOs and long-rod-like traces of melted GOs (x 250).

Figure 13 a: Scattered islands-like spots of unknown materials/or GOs (x 100). 13b: Scattered islands-like spots of unknown materials/or GOs and large island-like partially melted GOs with questionable secondary formation/or partially melted GOs (x 250).

Third group of HCQ treatment: All seven plasma samples from two COVID-19 experimental solution un-injected and five injected people showed similar patterns after HCQ treatments.

First case of the third group of HCQ treatment showed an axe-like or a finger-bone-like secondary GO structures with partially melted GO particles (x 250). Black clouds in the picture seem to be Foipan particles (Figures 15a,b).

Second case of the third group of HCQ treatment showed a group of melted GOs and an axe-like

secondary GO structures with partially melted GO particles (Left: x 100; Right: x 250) (Figures 16a,b).

Third case of the third group of HCQ treatment showed a bone-particle-like secondary GO structures with small secondary GO particles (x 250) (Figures 17a,b).

Fourth case of the third group of HCQ treatment showed an axe-like and a rectangular-bone-like secondary GO structure with partially melting secondary GO particles (x250) (Figures 18a,b).

Figure 14 a: Traces of completely melted GOs (x 100). 14b: Traces of completely melted GOs (x 250).

Figure 15 a: An axe-like secondary GO structure with partially melted GO particles (x 100). 15b: A finger-bone-like secondary GO structure with partially melted GO particles (x 250).

Figure 16 a: A group of melted GOs of 279 micrometers in length (x 100). 16b: An axe-like secondary GO structures with partially melted GO particles (x 250).

Figure 17 a: A bone-particle-like secondary GO structures of 339 micrometers and of 443 micrometers, and with a partially melted GO particle (x 100). 17b: A melted GO structures of 436 micrometers, a secondary GO structure of 197 micrometers with small secondary GO particles (x 250).

Fourth group of Ivermectin treatment: All seven plasma samples from two COVID-19 experimental solution un-injected and five injected people showed similar patterns after Ivermectin treatments.

First case of the fourth group of Ivermectin treatment showed spread out pebble-like, mostly melted GOs (x 100). Black clouds in the pictures seem to be Foipan particles (Figures 19a,b).

Second case of the fourth group of Ivermectin

treatment showed spread out pebble-like secondary GO structures (Left: x 250; Right: x 100). Black clouds in the pictures seem to be Foipan particles (Figures 20a,b).

Third case of the fourth group of Ivermectin treatment showed scattered pebble-like secondary GO structures with some other mostly melted GOs (Left: x 250; Right: x 100) (Figures 21a,b).

Fourth case of the fourth group of Ivermectin

Figure 18 a: An axe-like secondary GO structure with partially melted small secondary GO particles (x 250). 18b: A secondary GO structure of 436 micrometers x 136 micrometers with partially melted small secondary GO particles (x 250).

Figure 19 a: Spread out, pebble-like GOs, which were almost melted (x 250). 19b: Spread out pebble-like GOs, which were almost melted (x 100).

Figure 20 a: Spread out, round pebble-like secondary GOs, which were partially melted (x 100). 20b: Spread out, round pebble-like secondary GOs, which were partially melted (x 250).

treatment showed scattered pebble-like secondary GO structures with some other mostly melted GOs (Left: x 250; Right: x 100) (Figures 22a,b).

Fifth group of HCQ+ Ivermectin + Foipan treatment: All seven plasma samples from two COVID-19 experimental solution un-injected and five injected people showed similar patterns after HCQ+ Ivermectin + Foipan treatments.

First case of the fifth group of HCQ+ Ivermectin + Foipan treatment showed web-like secondary GO structures with partially melting GOs with vacuols.

(Left: x250, Right: x400). Black clouds in the pictures seem to be Foipan particles (Figures 23a,b).

Second case of the fifth group of HCQ+ Ivermectin + Foipan treatment showed pebble-like secondary GO structures with partially melting bony particle-like secondary GOs (Left: x 100, Right: x 250). Black clouds in the pictures seem to be Foipan particles (Figures 24a,b).

Third case of the fifth group of HCQ+ Ivermectin + Foipan treatment showed pebble-like secondary GO structures with partially melting gold particle-like

Figure 21 a: Spread out, round pebble-like secondary GOs, which were partially melted (x 100). 21b: Spread out, round pebble-like secondary GOs, which were partially melted (x 250).

Figure 22 a: Spred out, round pebble-like secondary GOs, which were partially melted (x 100). 22b: Spred out, round pebble-like secondary GOs, which were partially melted (x 250).

Figure 23 a: Web-like partially melting secondary GO structures with vacuols (x 250). 23b: A web-like partially melting secondary GO structure with vacuols (x 400).

Figure 24 a: Spred out, round pebble-like secondary GOs with partially melting gold particle-like larger secondary GOs of 165 micrometers, 97 micrometers, 63 micrometers, and 57 micrometers (x 100). 24b: Spred out, round pebble-like secondary GOs with partially melting gold particle-like larger secondary GOs of 251 micrometers, 228 micrometers and 200 micrometers (x 250).

GOs (x 250). Black clouds in the pictures seem to be Foipan particles (Figures 25a,b).

Sixth group of Gold Nanoparticle (GNP) + Foipan treatment: All seven plasma samples from two COVID-19 experimental solution un-injected and five injected people showed similar patterns after GNP + Foipan treatments.

First case of the sixth group of GNP + Foipan treatment showed partially melting rectangular

secondary GO structures (x 250) and a relatively clear background of a compact pebble-field-like melted GOs or unknown structures (x 250). Black clouds in the pictures seem to be Foipan particles (Figures 26a,b).

Second case of the sixth group of GNP + Foipan treatment showed partially melted rod-like secondary GO structures with relatively clear background of traces of melted GOs (x250). Black clouds in the pictures seem to be Foipan particles (Figures 27a,b).

Figure 25 a: Spread out, round pebble-like secondary GOs with a partially melting gold particle-like irregular-shaped secondary GO of 235 micrometers, and a partially melting gold particle-like round secondary GO of a 204 micrometer-diameter (x 250). 25b: Spread out, round pebble-like secondary GOs with partially melting gold particle-like larger secondary GOs of 417 micrometers x 340 micrometers, 95 micrometers, and 48 micrometers (x 250).

Figure 26 a: Partially melting rectangular secondary GO structures (x 250). 26b: A relatively clear background with compact pebble-field-like melted GOs or unknown structures (x 250).

Third case of the sixth group of GNP + Foipan treatment showed a satellite-like figure of partially melted rectangular secondary GO structures with relatively clear background of traces of melted GOs (x 250). Black clouds in the pictures seem to be Foipan particles and round black-disc like structures with a brownish-colored ring seem to be fungal contamination (Figures 28a,b).

Fourth case of the sixth group of GNP + Foipan treatment showed mostly melted sand-like secondary GO structures with relatively clear background of melted GOs. (Left: x 250). An oval-shape melted GO (235 x 250 micrometers) was seen in the background of sand-like melted GOs (Right: x 250). Black clouds in the pictures seem to be Foipan particles (Figures 29a,b).

Fifth case of the sixth group of GNP + Foipan treatment showed mostly melted oval GOs in a relatively background of many small bubble-like spots (x 100) and partially melted rectangular secondary GO structures in a relatively clear background of traces of

melted GOs (x 250). Black clouds in the picture seem to be Foipan particles (Figures 30a,b).

Sixth case of the sixth group of GNP + Foipan treatment showed almost melted large (Left: 1,300 x 650 micrometers in x 100, and Right: 810 micrometer in x 100) remnant plate of secondary GO structures with a relatively clear background of spots of melted GOs. Black clouds in the pictures seem to be Foipan particles (Figures 31a,b).

Seventh case of the sixth group of GNP + Foipan treatment showed sand island-like remnants of GOs against a relatively clear background (x 100). Four linear trails of partially melted remnants of GOs against a relatively clear background (x 100). Black clouds in the pictures seem to be Foipan particles (Figures 32a,b).

Third observational study

The first case of the third observational study was done with the plasma of a 66-year-old male, who was neither injected of the COVID-19 experimental injection (or bioweapon) nor had PCR tests.

Figure 27 a: Partially melting rod-like secondary GO structures (x 250). 27b: A relatively clear background with almost melted GOs or unknown structures (x 250).

Figure 28 a: A satellite-like figure with melted secondary GO structures of a rectangular shape in a relatively clear background (x 250). 28b: A relatively clear background with melted secondary GO structures of a rectangular shape (x 250).

Figure 29 a: Mostly melted sand-like secondary GO structures of a long trace (1,518 micrometers long) and of flower-like panning outs (63 micrometers and 168 micrometers) in a relatively clear background (x 250). 29b: An oval-shape melted GO (235 x 250 micrometers) was seen in the background of sand-like melted GOs (x 250).

Figure 30 a: Mostly melted oval GOs of 89 micrometers, 88 micrometers, and 40 micrometers in a relatively clear background of many spotted small bubble-like materials (x 100). 30b: Partially melted rectangular secondary GO structures in a relatively clear background of traces of melted GOs (x 250).

Figure 31 a: Almost melted large (1,397 x 847 micrometers) remnant plate of secondary GO structures with a relatively clear background of spots of melted GOs or unknown materials (x 100). 31b: Almost melted large (810 micrometers) GOs or unknown materials (x 250).

Figure 32 a: Sand island-like remnants of GOs in a relatively clear background (x 100). 32b: A trousers-like almost melted GOs in a relatively clear background with unknown spotted materials (x 100).

The plasma of the first case was observed before the treatment (Figures 33a,b).

The plasma was divided into two and was treated separately thrice a week for two weeks either with MMS2 or GNP + Foipan for two weeks (Figures 34a,b).

The second case of the third observational study was done with the plasma of a 54-year-old female, who was neither injected of the COVID-19 experimental injection (or bioweapon) nor had PCR tests. The plasma of the second case was observed before the treatment (Figures 35a,b).

The plasma was divided into two and was treated separately thrice a week for two weeks either with MMS2 or GNP + Foipan for two weeks (Figures 36a,b).

The third case of the third observational study was done in the plasma of a 52-year-old female, who was twice injected of the COVID-19 experimental injection (or bioweapon) and had several PCR tests. She had palpitations, dyspnea, generalized weakness, and loss of appetite when she visited out clinic. The plasma of the second case was observed before the treatment (Figures 37a,b).

The plasma was divided into two and was treated separately thrice a week for two weeks either with MMS2 or GNP + Foipan (Figures 38a,b).

The fourth case of the third observational study was done in the plasma of a 58-year-old female, who was twice injected of the COVID-19 experimental injection (or bioweapon) and had two PCR tests. She had Sjogren syndrome before the COVID-19 injections. She had dry eyes, mild dry mouth symptoms, and a generalized weakness when she visited our clinic. The plasma of the fourth case was observed before the treatment (Figures 39a,b).

The plasma was divided into two and was treated separately thrice a week for two weeks either with MMS2 or GNP + Foipan (Figures 40a,b).

The fifth case of the third observational study was done in the plasma of a 79-year-old female, who was twice injected of the COVID-19 experimental injection (or bioweapon) and had several PCR tests. She had intermittent muscle tremors and left chest pain with dyspnea when she visited our clinic. The plasma of the fifth case was observed before the treatment (Figures 41a,b).

Figure 33 a: A long-ribbon-like GO of 2.268 micrometers and a small GO beside of it were found in the plasma of a 66-year-old male before the treatment (x 100). 33b: A flying seagull-like GO of 757 micrometers in a relatively clear background (x 100).

Figure 34 a: MMS2 treatment showed almost clear background of melted GOs (x 250). 34b: GNP + Foipan treatment showed several melted secondary structures of GOs of 241 micrometers, 167 micrometers, 102 micrometers, 81 micrometers, and 79 micrometers (x 250). Black clouds in the pictures seem to be Foipan particles.

Figure 35 a: About 850 micrometers long-island-like GOs were found in the plasma of a 54-year-old female before the treatment (x 250). 35b: A sand-island-like melted GOs in a relatively clear background (x 400).

The plasma was divided into two and was treated separately thrice a week for 2 weeks either with MMS2 or GNP + Foipan (Figures 42a,b).

The sixth case of the third observational study was done in the plasma of a 25-year-old female, who was twice injected of the COVID-19 experimental injection (or bioweapon) and had several PCR tests. She had continuous vaginal bleeding with menstrual

irregularities. The plasma of the sixth case was observed before the treatment (Figures 43a,b).

The plasma was divided into two and was treated separately thrice a week for two weeks either with MMS2 or GNP + Foipan (Figures 44a,b)**Discussion**

Our observational studies showed that MMS2 was an excellent candidate for the detoxification of GOs in the plasma and that MMS2 could be one of possible

Figure 36 a: MMS2 treatment showed an almost clear background with melted GOs of 101 micrometers and 30 micrometers (x 250). 36b: GNP + Foipan treatment showed a secondary structure of 375 micrometer-length melted GO, and many groups of melted GOs of 178 micrometers, 147 micrometers, 144 micrometers, and 127 micrometers (x 250).

Figure 37 a: A 180 micrometer-sized GO particle was shown in a clear background (x 250). 37b: A taxiway-like of an airport, secondary GOs of lengths of 1,130 x 1,001 micrometers was shown (x 250).

Figure 38 a: MMS2 treatment showed melted GOs of 95 micrometers and of 62 micrometers in an almost clear background (x 250). 38b: GNP + Foipan treatment showed a melted-secondary-structures of GOs of 437 micrometers and 203 micrometers, and several groups of melted GOs of 393 micrometers and 91 micrometers (x 250). Black clouds in the pictures seem to be Foipan particles.

solutions for relieving symptoms of the COVID-19 experimental injection sequelae. For example, a 63-year-old woman, who was shocked when a spoon was stuck to her arm, expressed her joy when spoons did not attach to her arms any further after she took 8 drops a day of diluted MMS2 for two weeks. But here, we need to pay a caution to differentiate between MMS1 and MMS2. Even though MMS1 can be used for these purposes, MMS2 is rather recommended than

MMS1 because MMS1 is very hazardous and hard to handle.

MMS or MMS1 (Master Mineral Solution 1, Sodium Chlorite)

Sodium chlorite (NaClO_2) is also called as Master Mineral Solution 1 (MMS1), Miracle Mineral Supplement, Chlorine Dioxide Protocol, and Water Purification Solution. These are the different names of the same

Figure 39 a: A 760 micrometer-sized thick GO particle was seen in a clear background of plasma (x 250). 39b: Several GOs of 148 micrometers, 90 micrometers, and 30 micrometers were shown in the plasma of a 58-year-old female (x 250).

Figure 40 a: MMS2 treatment showed melted GOs of in an almost clear background (x 250). 40b: GNP + Foipan treatment showed round secondary-structures of GO of 104 micrometers and 103 micrometers, and an island-like group of melted GOs of 220 micrometers (x 250). Black clouds in the pictures seem to be Foipan particles.

Figure 41 a: A 117 micrometer-sized GO particle was seen in a relatively clear background of plasma (x 250). 41b: Several small GOs of a various size against a sand field-like melted background of GOs were shown in the plasma of a 79-year-old female (x 250).

material, Sodium chlorite (NaClO_2), which is a potentially dangerous one which requires a skillful and careful storage and handling, and is supplied either as a solid or a solution [12]. It is usually prepared as a white flaky salt of 80% concentration. It can make a violent reaction and explode on contact with organic substances such as clothing and gloves, oil and grease, and even sawdust and cotton waste. Because the solid sodium chlorite can explode by heat, friction or high impact, it should be dissolved in water and handled as a liquid form of sodium chlorite.

Jim Humble introduced protocol 1000 plus by adding dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) to the MMS (actually, MMS1) in a 3:1 ratio (i.e., 6 drops of DMSO to 2 drops of MMS) and said that it is potent as an antifungal, for healings of nerve and tissue, for encouraging the homeostasis of a human body [13] It has protocols for helping diabetic foot ulcers, flesh-eating bacterial disease, rabies and tetanus, autoimmune thyroid disease, post-vaccine thyroid storm, Alzheimer's dementia, heart attacks in South Korea, Jim Humble's protocol has been used as one

Figure 43 a: A 634 micrometer-sized thick GO particle with a branch was shown in a clear background (x 250). 43b: An S-shape-curved of a 1,006 micrometer-sized thick GO with three branches was shown (x 250).

Figure 44 a: MMS2 treatment showed three small groups of melted remnants of GOs of 226 micrometers, 224 micrometer, and 144 micrometers in a relatively clear background (x 250). 44b: GNP + Foipan treatment showed six groups of melted speckles of GOs of 325 micrometers, 237 micrometer, 226 micrometer, 212 micrometer, 131 micrometer, and 96 micrometers in a relatively clear background (x 250). Black clouds in the pictures seem to be Foipan particles.

of the folk remedies specially to detoxify sequels of COVID-19 experimental injections and there are many internet blog sites of introducing the making method of MMS detoxifying solution [14]. But there was not a MMS1-related article regarding the detoxification of COVID-19 experimental injections or graphene oxide which is the main component of COVID-19 experimental injections. In addition, many people are reluctant to take MMS1 as a detoxifying agent because the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) warned that sodium chlorite was not approved for drinking or helping to treat autism, cancer, HIV/AIDS, acne, allergies, arthritis, bronchitis, *Candida albicans*, cardiovascular disease, chronic fatigue, chronic pain, COVID-19, cystitis, depression, and flu [15]. Hence, MMS2 solution was tested for the detoxification of GOs in the plasma and for the eradication of COVID-19-related symptoms.

MMS2 (Master Mineral Solution 2, Calcium hypochlorite)

Calcium hypochlorite (MMS2, Drinking Water Disinfection Solution) should be differentiated from

Sodium chlorite (MMS1, Miracle Mineral Solution, Miracle Mineral Supplement, Chloride Dioxide Protocol, Water Purification Solution). In contrast to MMS1 (Sodium chlorite, NaClO_2), MMS2 (calcium hypochlorite) or $\text{Ca}(\text{ClO})_2$ was recommended by U.S. Army Center for Health Promotion and Preventive Medicine. U.S. Army Center for Health Promotion and Preventive Medicine issued standards for use of calcium hypochlorite for drinking water disinfection in the military in 2003, which was reissued by the Departments of the Army, Navy, and Air Force on May 1, 2010 in the book of Sanitary Control and Surveillance of Field Water Supplies. U.S. Army Center recommended a method for the making of stock solution of calcium hypochlorite [16]. Calcium hypochlorite dissolves in water and forms a strong oxidant, hypochlorous acid (HOCl), $\text{HOCl} \leftrightarrow \text{hypochlorite}, \text{OCl}^- + \text{H}^+$. Myeloperoxidase are produced by neutrophils, eosinophils, mononuclear phagocytes and B lymphocyte when a human being is exposed to infection, injury, and are poured into the blood stream to make hypochlorous acid, which is a strong oxidant and which is the same one made by calcium hypochlorite [17,18]. On the other hand,

because Hypochlorous acid (HOCl) can form a secondary radical of strong oxidants, it has cytotoxic effects and can cause various diseases such as cancer, atherosclerosis, emphysema, arthritis, asthma, ageing, hypertension, cirrhosis, allergy, cataract, retinopathy, and macular disease [19]. So, one and half hour after drinking MMS2, oral intaking of Vit C 2 gr is recommended in our clinic.

Other methods to detoxify GOs in the plasma

A group of people argued that there were evidences of GO in COVID-19 vaccines, Flu vaccines, chem trails, rainwater post chem trail spraying by airplanes, and in a lipid compound of PEG (polyethylene glycol). Some saline injections or aqueous medical injections were questioned to have graphene oxide, which can transform the bodies of the injected people to attach spoons, metal materials on their arms, foreheads, faces, and belly (This is what one of my patients experienced) [20].

NAC (N-acetyl cysteine) adhered to the rGO (reduced GO) surface, avoided GO-mediated oxidation of glutathione, and detoxified GO [21]. Tony Patallesco made a bucket wrapped in wire to remove synthetic-biology-made nanomaterials from our body, because he thought that our bodies were swamped with nanomaterials which could change our DNA, make blood clots, and deprive many essential minerals from our bodies [22]. He recommended foot baths (in water with Bentonite clay or Epsom salt) to get rid of foreign nanomaterials. This kind of detoxifying foot bath is well-known in Korea and there was a report that lots of visible foreign beings were extracted from foot baths. Many parasite-like living organisms with egg-pouch, Morgellons with hair-like GO and egg-pouch, and synthetic foreign materials were found in the detoxifying foot bath. And a kind of a detoxifying method was recommended in the table [6] and revised [11]. The latter article recommended local food supplements: Smart Food DM; Hamssine mouse-eyed bean, garlic, and bean paste; EGCG (epi-gallocatechine-3-gallate in green tea, apples, blueberries, carob flour, blackberries, nuts, peaches, avocados, onion, raspberries, and plums), Chitosan, turmeric (in curry), resveratrol (in cran-/blueberries, grapes, peanuts, wines). Naturopathy and homeopathy groups provided a list of various natural foods, supplements, and methods to remove GOs and toxic materials from our body and to increase our natural immunity: Silica D homeopathic; Potassium; Krill Oil; Bentonite Clay, in water or foot baths; Epsom

salt foot baths; Colloidal Silver; Chlorella; Spirulina; Garlic; Shitake Mushrooms; Tea Tree Oil; Oil of Oregano; Cilantro Lime; Ginger; Evening Primrose Oil [22].

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